

Research

Facile deposition of GaAs thin film on glass substrate via post annealing in open air

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Abstract: Gallium arsenide (GaAs) films were grown on glass substrates by resistive heating technique under a vacuum pressure 7.6×10^{-5} mbar at room temperature. In an open environment, samples were post-annealed at the temperature 250°C, 280°C, and 320°C in a homemade tube furnace. Different characterizations of all post-annealed GaAs samples were done through X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS). XRD analysis showed that the material has polycrystalline textures. Surface morphological structures were characterized by SEM. Elemental compositions were done by EDX and RBS, no evidence of contaminations found. Moreover, we derived that the post-annealing treatment was not affecting the GaAs thin films in an open environment.

Keywords: Gallium arsenide, thin film deposition, Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS), resistive heating technique

Introduction

Since 1920 Goldschmidt has been discovered Gallium Arsenide and later confirmed it in 1929 [1]. GaAs is a compound semiconductor. Gallium has extracted from various materials such as zinc ores and bauxite and more valuable than gold. Arsenic is toxic, but ordinary material. GaAs has a crystal shape known sphalerite (zinc blende) lattice [2, 3]. Practical applications of Gallium Arsenide are photovoltaic, high brightness LEDs and, ultimately, all optical space switch technologies [4]. The bandgap of GaAs is 1.42eV which is closer to the standard band gap energy

of 1.5eV for solar energy conversion [5]. It is broadly used in the semiconductor fabrication due to its extensive direct band gap energy and higher electron mobility than Si [6]. GaAs has high radiation tolerance and efficiency as compared to other solar cells. Due to this reason in 1980s Radio Corporation of America and USA States Department of Defense first used GaAs as a microprocessor for Star Wars programs [6]. It is used in various applications such as beam combiners, beam splitters, and polarizers as substrates [7, 8]. The amorphous and crystalline thin film of GaAs on different substrates has been formed with various methods, such as electron beam evaporation, sputtering, molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) and pulsed laser deposition (PLD) [9]. Diverse applications of GaAs are well fitted with advanced future technology such that electronics, optoelectronics, and thin film applications.

In this research work, GaAs samples were prepared by a resistive heating evaporation technique. Furthermore, we have explored first time the effect of annealing in an open air of GaAs films and also characterized the same samples with help of RBS and EDS to find out the comparative effect of elemental compositions. We have also verified in detail all samples with the help of XRD, SEM, EDS, and RBS.

Crystallinities of post-annealed films were evaluated by XRD. X-ray diffractometer (JEOL JDX3532), using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ energy emissions ($\lambda = 0.154 \text{ nm}$). Surface morphologies and structures of films were carried out by Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL JSM5910). The samples composition carried out by EDX. The samples thickness and sample elemental composition analysis also were determined by Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry (RBS) technique. RBS experimental details as following, accelerator (5MV Pelletron Tandem Accelerator), beam (He^{++}), energy (2.084 MeV), detector (Solid State Barrier (SSB)), resolution of detector (20 KeV), backscattering angle (170°), incident angle (0°), charge (15 μC), current (26 nA), Software (RC43, XRUMP, SIMNRA).

Experimental details

First of all, keep the glass substrates in acetone and then in deionized water into an ultrasonic vessel for 20 minutes each to remove contaminations. Clean substrates keep in a suitable environment at room temperature before using for evaporation. In this experiment resistive heating evaporation unit “*EdwardE306A, UK*” was used as shown in figure 1. Glass slides used as substrates; multi substrates kept inside the substrate rotor. The GaAs powder purity (99.999%,

Beijing Goodwill Metal Technology Co. Ltd) keeps in tantalum (Ta) foil boat. The distance between substrates rotor and boat has round about 5cm and rotor located opposite to the boat. GaAs thin film on glass substrates was grown under a vacuum pressure 7.6×10^{-5} mbar at room temperature and deposition time has count just 6 minutes. After that, we have selected three most suitable samples for further characterizations. Furthermore, keep the samples one by one in homemade tube furnace (maximum range 1400°C) in an open air each for 20 minutes annealing. The reading of annealing temperatures was 250°C for sample 250, 280°C for sample 280 and 320°C for sample 320.

Figure 1. (a) Resistive heating evaporation unit “EdwardE306A, UK” (b) Schematic diagram of glass bell jar or vacuum chamber(c) Homemade tube furnace (max range 1400 °C) (d) XRD of GaAs/glass of samples 250, 280, and 320.

Results and discussion

XRD is a nondestructive technique devoted to finding crystal structure and crystallite sizes of the as-grown thin films [10, 11]. A crystallite grain size of film is determined by Scherrer’s formula [12] as follows

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\Delta(2\theta) \cos \theta}$$

Where “D” is for crystallite grain size, “K” is constant and ordinary value is 0.9, “λ” is the wavelength of X-ray using (λ= 0.1540556nm), Δ (2θ) is full width at half maxima of the peak (FWHM) in radians, “θ” is peak position in degrees. XRD graph of Gallium Arsenide on glass substrates as shown in figure 1(d). Narrow peaks of post-annealed sample 250 were given at 27.35° degrees which specified proper film crystallinity [13, 14]. Hence, it is a preferential matching plane is (111). The grain size determined by Scherrer’s formula which has 52.68 nm [15]. Similarly, sample 280 peak at 27.42° is matching to (111) plane and grain size is round about 57.35 nm and sample 320 peak at 27.43° and crystal size has 57.58 nm approximately. Therefore, we have generalized that it depends on annealing temperature [16]. At high annealing, as compared to lower annealing the ratio of crystallinities becomes increases [17].

SEM is using to find out surface morphology and topography structures, cracks, porosities and grain size, etc., [18]. SEM images of the surfaces of samples 250, 280, and 320 in various series of exposure and determination have shown in figure 2 [19]. Surface morphological pictures of GaAs films have specified that it depends on the annealing temperature. Due to the increases in annealing temperature, the under coordination defect of GaAs film like wrong bonds (Ga-Ga and As-As) and dangling bonds (db-Ga and db-As) become decreases. Therefore, gap states, surface of film and the size of grains become polished [20]. Slightly differences have appeared when the temperature values such that 250°C, 280°C, and 320°C have shifted from lower to higher mentioned in figure 2. Moreover, their roughness and porosities have covered. There were some cracks seems in figures 2(d) of both sample 280 and sample 320, maybe the cracks have occurred from high annealing in open environment or using a heavy dose of electron beam irradiation during magnifications but still, the mechanism is unknown.

Figure 2. Surface morphological of GaAs/glass of sample 250, sample 280, and sample 320 at 5 μm, 1 μm, 0.5 μm, 0.2 μm ranges by SEM.

EDS is a non-destructive technique that is used for identifications of elements in the grown film. It can identify only elements from beryllium (Be) to uranium (U) in the periodic table [21]. It's also a counterpart of SEM in which sample was bombarded with an electron beam inside SEM to eliminated a few electrons from the surface of the sample. During the transition of electrons from the inner shell to outer shell, leaving some vacancies and gives up more energy in the shape of X-rays. Every peak has a specified single element and the element whose peak higher will consider a dominant element in EDS spectrum. EDS graph was not just described elemental peaks but also categorizes the transition of X-ray during emission [14]. A GaAs/glass film has shown in figure 3 carried out by EDX. All three samples have formed in the same environment and treated with different values. Post-annealing treatment values were 250°C, 280°C, and 320°C which have done in open environment each for 20 minutes into a homemade tube furnace. Concentrations of Ga and As in all three samples have approximately equal and no evidence of contaminations found, shown

in figure 3. Hence annealing in an open environment of GaAs gets no contamination. Normally, the X-ray transitions have different series such that K series for light elements, L series for intermediate and M series for heavy elements. Experimental results mentioned in figure 3, in which transition of X-rays series matched with L series it means that GaAs has an intermediate material [22, 23].

Figure 3. EDX spectrum and elemental compositions (a) Samples 250 (b) Sample 280 and (c) Sample 320.

Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy is a nondestructive technique that is used for film quantities depth profiling as well as compositional determination of elements such that area concentration measurements ($\text{atoms}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). RBS is also used for measuring film contamination and crystal structures. In this technique normally we have used high energy ion beams like He^{++} ion with the energies of 2.084 MeV as probes. RBS has high penetration capability to move into

sample several thousands of angstroms. The film thickness has determined from peak width and elemental compositions of the film from the peak yields. RBS has a hundred times more suitable for light elements rather than heavy elements. It means that RBS has an excellent mass resolution for light elements as compared to heavy elements. GaAs has an intermediate material already discussed in EDS result. Thickness analysis of GaAs/glass films has determined with the help of RBS technique. Comparative study of samples 250, 280, and 320 have shown in figures 4, seems slightly difference due to area concentration of atoms-cm⁻² and peaks width shows film thickness [24]. GaAs/glass composition has presented in the table shown in figure 4(d). We also concluded that a thin film of GaAs/glass got no impurity. Moreover, RBS analysis has shown that resistive heating evaporation has a non-homogenous film technique because each sample has a different film thickness.

Figure 4. RBS spectrum of (a) Sample 250 (b) Sample 280 (c) Sample 320 and (d) Composition ratios, and film thickness of samples 250, 280 and 320 and glass substrates.

Conclusions

In this research work, GaAs powder was deposited on glass substrates through resistive heating evaporation technique in the presence of 7.6×10^{-5} mbar vacuum pressure at room temperature. All three samples were annealed 20 minutes separately in an open environment in a homemade tube furnace at 250°C temperature for sample 250, 280°C temperature for sample 280 and 320°C temperature for sample 320. Each sample was characterized by different techniques such that XRD, SEM, EXD, RBS. In XRD we have calculated the crystal size with helped of Scherrer's formula which has an excellent matched with literature. SEM has shown good results, but unfortunately, we have found some cracks in the resolution range 0.2 μm in sample 280 and sample 320, maybe the reason of annealed in an open environment or high dosed electron beam irradiation but the exact mechanism still unknown. The identification of elements of grown films has done by EDX and no evidenced of contamination have found. We derived that in an open environment annealing of GaAs has not affected by any contamination. We have also found that GaAs is an intermediate material because of L series X-rays transitions. We have also confirmed first time the elemental composition and sample thickness with the help of RBS. In RBS peaks all samples have shown slightly difference in peaks and random thickness but no contamination found. It means that the resistive heating evaporation technique has a non-homogenous film technique due to the random thickness of all samples.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare

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